

AMNIOTIC BAND SYNDROME AS A CAUSE OF ECTOPIA CORDIS THORACALIS AND OTHER CRANIOFACIAL DEFECTS

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ABSTRACT A 24-week gestation fetus, on ultrasound, was found to have Ectopia Cordis, besides other anomalies like frontonasal dysgenesis, facial cleft, hydrocephalus and a distorted skull vault. Fibrous bands were seen to be attached to the apex of the heart, face, and placenta. Isolated Ectopia Cordis occurs due to malformed thoracic chest wall during early embryogenesis. However, fibrous bands adherent to the heart causing mechanical forces may also lead to ectopia cordis, referred to as mechanical teratogenesis. These amniotic bands are formed due to early rupture of chorion or amnion in embryogenesis, and a spectrum of defects is found following it, the variety of which is based upon the timing of rupture. As is illustrated by our ultrasound pictures and clinical specimens, a cephalic pointing cardiac apex secondary to tethering of the heart to the frontonasal region of the face by amniotic bands could be the aetiology of this thoracoabdominal ectopia cordis. Thus Ectopia Cordis with amniotic bands appears to have an aetiology entirely different from isolated ectopia cordis. This suggests distinct etiologies for ectopia cordis, and in the light of literature, they have been discussed with this case report.

KEYWORDS Ectopia Cordis, Amniotic Band Syndrome, mechanical teratogenesis

Introduction

Ectopia Cordis is defined as a condition in which the heart lies outside the thoracic cavity, either partially or entirely. It is thought to occur due to the failure of proper maturation of midline mesoderm and improper ventral body wall formation during embryonic development. Another aetiology of Ectopia cordis is the Amniotic Band Syndrome in which there is an early rupture of chorion or amnion leading to the formation of fibrous bands that entangle various developing fetal parts leading to deformation and malformations. Thus Amniotic Band Syndrome

is believed to be the mechanical cause of Ectopia Cordis in utero. We report one such rare case in which Ectopia Cordis was diagnosed antenatally on USG and MRI in a 24-week old fetus along with the presence of amniotic bands and other craniofacial abnormalities.

Case Report

26-year-old primigravida female with 25 weeks of amenorrhea and only one ultrasound scan at eight weeks, presented to the hospital with the chief complaints of PV leak. The patient had no significant medical history or co-morbidities and was not on any medications. Ultrasound scanning for fetal viability and well-being was done. The fetus was found to be of a gestational age of about 24 weeks. The skull vault of the fetus was distorted with gross dilatation of bilateral lateral ventricles in the brain and thinning of cortex [Figure 1]. Third and fourth ventricles, posterior fossa and spine were normal. The fetus was alive. However, the heart of the fetus was seen protruding out of the thoracic wall and was entirely placed outside the thorax which suggested Ectopia Cordis [Figure 2]. It was covered with pericardium, but it was not covered with skin. A band like

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Fig.1. Ultrasound image through the fetal head showing dilatation of the bilateral lateral ventricles in brain suggestive of Hydrocephalus

structure was seen attached to the apex of the heart, and its other end was seen to be attached to the upper part of the face in the region of nose [Figure 3]. On careful examination, fetal face morphology appeared distorted with cleft lip and palate towards left side of face. Reduced Liquor with open internal os was seen. Patient was taken for fetal MRI to find out the cause of hydrocephalus and diagnose any additional anomaly. MRI showed the presence of hydrocephalus, ectopia cordis and other facial dysmorphic features [Figure 4,5]. However, the cause of hydrocephalus could not be elicited.

The fetus was spontaneously aborted in 24 hours, and the delivery was uneventful. The fetus did not survive post-delivery. It was found to have similar findings as observed on ultrasound. The head was enlarged; there was frontonasal dysgenesis with the rudimentary eye, cleft lip and cleft palate. The heart was lying outside the thoracic cavity, turned vertically upside down and there were two bands seen attached to the fetus. One band connected the apex of the heart to the fronto-nasal process causing the apex of the heart to be pulled up cranially because of traction. Another band was seen attached to the same fronto-nasal region and other end attached to the placenta [Figure 6]. There were no abnormalities of limbs noted in the fetus. Plain radiograph of the fetus was taken. It showed the absence of sternal ossification centres in the thoracic cage. However, ribs were seen to be ossified [Figure 7].

Discussion

Ectopia cordis is a congenital anomaly characterised by complete or partial protrusion of heart through a defect in the thoracoabdominal wall. Haller et al. first described it in 1706 [1]. An antenatal ultrasound scan helps in establishing the diagnosis of ectopia cordis, and early diagnosis can lead to appropriate management.

It is a rare congenital development disorder having an inci-

Fig.2.A. Ultrasound image through the fetal thorax showing complete herniation of heart outside the thoracic cavity suggesting Thoracic Ectopia Cordis.

Fig.2.B. Color Doppler image of the fetal ectopic heart showing normal colour flow pattern.

Fig.3. The ultrasound image is showing the presence of a band like structure attached from the cranially pulled apex of the heart to the face of the fetus.

Fig.5.A. T2 weighted Ssagittal sections of the fetus are demonstrating heart lying outside the thoracic cavity with aorta running posteriorly and inside through it.

Fig.4. T2 weighted axial sections of fetal MRI showing flow void of the protruded heart lying outside the body wall and aorta running inside through it.

Fig.5.B. Ectopic Heart is seen pulled cranially due to a thin septum attaching it to the frontonasal prominence on the other end.

Fig.6.A. Post-delivery image of the fetus showing the presence of heart outside the thorax.

Fig.6.B. Amniotic bands seen, one attached from apex of the heart and another from umbilical cord to frontonasal region.

Fig.7. Post-delivery radiograph of the fetus

dence of 5.5 to 7.9 per million live births [2]. It is classified into five types according to the location of the heart [2]:

1. Cervical (3%)- the heart is in the neck region while chest wall and sternum is intact;
2. Thoracocervical (<1%)- heart protrudes out through a defect in sternum in its superior portion;
3. Thoracic (60%)- heart protrudes out through a defect in sternum in its middle portion;
4. Thoracoabdominal (7%)- heart protrudes out through a defect in sternum in its lower portion. This can occur in association with other diaphragmatic and ventral wall defects;
5. Abdominal (30%)- there is a defect in the diaphragm and heart is displaced into the abdomen through it;

The exact aetiology of Ectopia cordis is not known. However it is primarily attributed to the failure of development of the thoracic cavity during embryogenesis (specifically 8th day of the embryonic life). The midline mesoderm fails to mature, and the ventral body wall development is compromised. The lateral body walls, which normally connect to the ventral wall, also fail to fuse. Thus an improper or incomplete fusion of the ventral walls occurs in the 9th week of life. This entity is termed as Isolated Ectopia Cordis.

In some extremely rare cases, it can also occur with other ventral wall defects leading to malpositioned viscera like omphalocele, diaphragmatic hernia, sternal cleft and other cardiovascular malformations, in which case it is called as Pentalogy of Cantrell.

Another theory states Amniotic band syndrome as a mechanical cause of ectopia cordis. This complex is embryologically distinct from Isolated ectopia cordis. According to it, there is an early rupture of chorion and yolk sac during embryogenesis.

The disrupted chorion then causes compression of the thorax that consequently arrests midline fusion.

Amniotic band syndrome per se is a group of birth malformations caused by the entrapment of the infant body parts in fibrous amniotic bands during development in-utero, which leads to constrictions and malformation. Digits, arms and legs are the common body parts to be involved however other defects like cleft lip, cleft palate, club hands and club feet can also occur. Depending on the region of attachment or constriction, webbing of the fingers or toes, limb amputations, craniofacial abnormalities, and visceral abnormalities may occur [2].

It is also proved in fetal rat studies that the ligature effect of amniotic bands can cause congenital limb ring-constrictions and the severity of the resultant limb ring constriction is related to the constricting force of such an amniotic band [3].

To understand the pathogenesis of amniotic band syndrome, various theories have been proposed. An Endogenous or the Intrinsic theory was proposed by Streeter [4], according to which the primary defect lies in the germinal disc [5].

However, the most accepted is the Extrinsic theory, proposed by Torpin [6], who established that intrinsic weakness, inflammation, or trauma could lead to early rupture of the amnion which initiates a cascade of secondary events. There is consequent leakage of fluid, leading to the introduction of the fetus into the chorionic cavity. The chorion reabsorbs this fluid as a result of which the proliferation of mesenchymal bands takes place. These bands entangle the fetus and limit its movements which may subsequently lead to mechanical constrictions [5]. He also proposed that Amniotic rupture which occurs early in gestation can cause multiple developmental malformations, whereas, rupture occurring later causes limb anomalies only [7].

Prochaska first reported the complex of ectopia cordis, craniofacial defects & amniotic bands in 1734. It is now known that it occurs due to mechanical teratogenesis induced by fibrous bands adherent to thorax, cranium or face leading to pressure necrosis & tethering of amnion leading to incomplete morphogenesis. The aetiology for rupture of amnion is unknown [8]. In this course, abnormal adhesion of the umbilical cord with fetal membranes can also occur, which prevents the mesodermal approximation of sternal plates, resulting in pulling of the heart [5].

In our present case, the possible reason for ectopia cordis and facial dysmorphogenesis could be the abnormal attachment of amniotic bands from the placental surface to frontonasal process and frontonasal process to the apex of the heart causing pulling up of the heart outside from the thoracic cavity. Thus it was established that it was not a case of Isolated Ectopia Cordis but a mechanical Ectopia Cordis that occurred due to Amniotic bands formation.

Isolated ectopia cordis with no intracardiac defects can be corrected by surgical repair; however surgical correction of these multiple defects is complex [9]. It can be done for cases with thoracic and thoracoabdominal ectopia cordis which have been reported to survive full cardiac, neurologic and abdominal repair during infancy [10].

Conclusion

We report a case of amniotic band syndrome as a cause of ectopia cordis in a 24-week old fetus. The fetus had hydrocephalus, thoracic type of ectopia cordis, frontonasal dysgenesis, facial cleft and a rudimentary eye. The multiple congenital deformities observed in this case may have been due to rupture of the amnion

occurring early in the gestation period leading to a proliferation of mesenchymal bands which may have entangled the fetus within them and thus resulted in the deformities.[5]

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